

Europeana Media

EUPS Requirements Catalogue

Document: MS 1 EUPS Requirements catalogue
Version 1.01 (29 January 2019)

Activity 1: 1 User stories and requirements definition

Produced under Grant agreement No INEA/CEF/ICT/A2017/1564684 Europeana Media
for the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
Department C - Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) - TELECOMMUNICATIONS SECTOR

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Activity 1: 1 User stories and requirements definition

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INTRODUCTION

The objective of this Europeana Media Action is to develop the Europeana Enhanced Unified Playback Service (EUPS): a high-quality universal player to play multimedia files (audio, music, video and movies) on Europeana. The player is expected to have a user-friendly design that meets the prospects and requirements of both the public at large and target user groups specifically addressed by Europeana (education and research). The new player attempts to address most of the challenges Europeana faces with regard to media playback: (1) the diversity of playback services currently used by content providers, (2) the lack of appealing and user-friendly features in the playback interface (especially for specialist audiences) and (3) the lack of visibility and clarity of information about potential media reuse. The aim of the EUPS will be to deliver functionalities to better access and incorporate AV content from Europeana into the working environments of researchers, educators and citizens.

In Europeana Media's Activity 1, the partners specifically research what functionalities users in general as well as those more specifically targeted by Europeana (the education and research communities) expect from such a Universal Player beyond those functionalities that have become common to media users. The use of analogue and digital recorders and players in the recent past (tape and cassette recorders, videorecorders, CD-, DVD- and BlueRay players) and in the digital era (Windows Media Player, QuickTime, iTunes, VLC media player) and media platforms such as YouTube and Vimeo have made all contemporary users familiar with common player functionalities. Basic functions include play, pause, fast forward, rewind and stop, in general represented by a common set of widely recognisable buttons or icons. In addition, digital players usually have progress bars to indicate the media's timespan and locate the current position of the "player head".

In addition to these basic functionalities, different players integrate additional functionalities. Some video players provide controls for zooming (full screen video view), picture quality control (colour control, picture sharpening) or support for subtitles. Some audio/video players provide functionalities such as a media library, playlists and indexing, tagging, lyric or artwork discovery, and editing. Some players even allow for basic recording, editing and sharing. Other functionalities that can be found are: time stretching, chapterisation, bookmarking, auto-resume, etc. The list of functionalities that can be found in the diverse players that are around is long, and there is not a single player configuration that includes all functionalities. Standalone players are the individual choice of the user, depending on the platform (operating system), the media type (codec, metadata) and the user's functional requirements. Media platforms such as YouTube and Vimeo offer the user media consumption experiences with many functionalities that are similar to what the user finds in standalone players and have led to an expansive set of minimal user expectations regarding the interface and functionality of the media player.

In order to complement standard player functionalities that satisfy most common (recreative) users of a media catalogue such as Europeana, and in order to select those functionalities that are relevant for key target users, in this first step specific information was collected from potential Europeana

users in the areas of education, research and Europeana Collections. A small but representative sample of users was surveyed regarding their typical usage behaviour, tasks, needs and expectations related to the functionalities of the EUPS. Activity 1 leader ATiT, together with TIB and Europeana, used in-depth interviews and surveys with real users from the three target groups (education, research and public) to extract realistic requirements for the EUPS.

In order to focus the interviews on player and interface functionalities that are technically achievable and do not raise unrealistic expectations with regard to Europeana's mission and constraints, the interview and survey questions were based on a previously prepared number of user stories that integrate functionalities that from the project start had been accepted by all partners in the project as desired or required, but that were at the same time realistic (with regard to, for example, copyrights) and technically achievable - taking into account the development resources available to the project team. This is because it would not have made sense to approach the user communities with a blank slate and ask them what they require and desire. Firstly, because video playout requirements have often been explored already, so it is largely known what users say in terms of what they want and need, and secondly, because the Europeana Media consortium knows the technical and legal constraints to what can be offered to the users. The project group agreed that presenting users with functionalities that were agreed upon beforehand (as described in the proposal in Part D under 1.2 Objectives of Europeana Media (table on page 6 to 8) and co-constructing the use cases around these functionalities would be much more relevant and productive in the short time available. Of course, this approach did not exclude unpredicted or unpredictable use cases or new user requirements: these were duly recorded and their applicability, potential and technical and legal achievability are taken into account by the project.

DEVELOPMENT OF USE CASES (VERSION 1)

Work on the extraction of user requirements started with the composition of a first version of a number of user stories. These stories were based on interviews with users from research and education and on the user needs analysis that was carried out in past research and development projects such as eStream, VideoActive, EduTubePlus, EUscreen and EUscreenPlus. The resulting user stories were the first basis for a discussion amongst the Europeana Media partners from the onset of the project. These initial versions can be found in Annex 1: User Stories (version 1). These user stories were informally agreed before the start of Europeana Media as the first common ground for further discussion.

FIRST LONG LIST OF FUNCTIONALITIES

A long list of functionalities was extracted from the user stories, which was provided to all partners for their review. This resulted in the following document, that was discussed in depth by all partners during the first face to face project meeting in Rome on 17 and 18 September 2018:

#	Primary functions	Location in the player	Sub-functions	Open Questions
01	Annotation and Tagging	Annotations button above workspace	text formatting? Arrow & other elements Tag/annotation list for fast navigation?	in Timeline or directly in the video? Annotate with markers/keyframes? Hotspots with external links? Private/shared/public annotations/tags? Store/share annotations/tags? Login required?
02	Interactive video?	?	Add hotspot add MCQ?	Is this achievable???
03	bibliographic metadata export to literature management system (e.g. Zotero)	Share-Button in the workspace		
04	DOI/MFID-Display	Meta-Data for the video		
05	Extract and download single images	Button in workspace		
06	Download	Button in workspace	Button active on condition (Copyright) Select Download flavour	Login required?

#	Primary functions	Location in the player	Sub-functions	Open Questions
07	Embed video function and settings	Share-Button in workspace	<> Embedding Start at [time] Player-controls show/hide show Video title and Player-Action	Also share-button (Permalink, Social-Media, email)? (Also embed in PPT with embed code)
08	Licence-/Copyright-Information	Meta-Data for Video		
09	Overviews of scenes with Thumbnails	Integrated in the player		
10	Subtitles (original language transcript, new language versions)	Next to Video Display (button on / off)	Transcript with / without timestamp Download transcript/subtitles (select file format)?	Automatic Speech to Text (creates possibilities for in content search)? Enable user-generated transcript and/or subtitles Store, share/publish (conditional see Copyright)?
11	Video Segmentation	Below video display		User can store segmentation and recall Share, embed, download (conditionally) (Login required?)
12	Zoom and slow-motion function			
13	10 secs forward or backwards			
14	Account/profile?			Login required?

#	Primary functions	Location in the player	Sub-functions	Open Questions
15	Create playlist	Button in workspace		Store/copy/edit/share playlist? Login required?

Table 1: Functionalities described in Part D under 1.2 Objectives of Europeana Media

LONG LIST OF FUNCTIONALITIES - REVIEWED

The discussion at the Rome meeting resulted in a new version of the list of functionalities:

Func tion #	Primary function	Discussion	Examples
00	Asking for permissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europeana: has to be all or nothing, no custom development • Interventions vs adding information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europeana's new item page: download button, expand / collapse
01	Annotation and Tagging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design issue: Europeana re-developing their item page layout • Player would be embeddable - how many functions move along with it • Owner side: Do the content providers allow it? (who takes care of this layer?) • Who can share annotations with whom 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VIAA teacher site (HiHaHo) • IIF Annotations API • 3d party services • CLARIAH Mediasuite • Frametrail • Hypothes.is
02	Hotspot / Interactive video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storing comments - UGC on Europeana platform or separate? Currently • Does the hotspot move with the subject? • Noterik platform allows metadata linked to time - Europeana Annotations API is not finite, will need to be extended to new features • Enable the embed to do more / talking back • Rename: smart embed / interactive embed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soundcloud • HiHaHo • Vialogues • Exhausting a Crowd • MuPop / Qanda
03	Bibliographic metadata export	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At item level for Europeana 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TIB AV Portal
04	DOI/MFID-Display	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI-based - Europeana citations working group will come with recommendations in 4 - 5 months • Not on Europeana's roadmap - but would be available in the data that are ingested and could be made available in EDM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • x-headers

Func tion #	Primary function	Discussion	Examples
05	Extract and download single images	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUscreen extracts them for every second • Only display when CC • Button in workspace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making GIFs?
06	Download	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Already on Europeana roadmap - conditional download can filter correctly? Ash is checking business logic. • Core feature => copyright protection • No live transcodes - only one flavour available in EDM • Web resource logic is <u>not</u> copyright-based <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Not downloadable if no URL ○ Not downloadable if iif or oEmbed ○ NDI MIME type is text ○ Downloadable if source is shown in EDM 	
07	Embed video function and settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filtered based on rights statement • Develop in player and offer functionality to selected providers 	
08	Licence-/Copyright-Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarify what user can / cannot do (sub-activities) with implication for what user can do • Loop around with content partners (cfr. EUscreen) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See list below
09	Overviews of scenes with Thumbnails	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impossible without having source content 	
10	Subtitles (original language transcript, new language versions)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display is not problematic • Are there tools for getting the data in Europeana? • Allow content owners to upload • Allow users to update / create • Europeana Allow API to enable upload? • Making them searchable (via annotation API) - with what user experience? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <insert content into web page?> • Daniel idea: store information locally in browser in html5 • Make use of extraction services? TIB developing a service for German libraries • Allow user to translate only a piece of the video? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TED.com • Mind of the Universe • TIB AV • IIF? • Amara, UPV,

Func tion #	Primary function	Discussion	Examples
11	Video Segmentati on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Out of scope 	
12	Zoom and slow- motion function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within limits of what works and why (backwards is tricky) 	
13	10 secs forward or backwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quite common - layering on top of underlying streaming functionality 	
14	Account/pr ofile?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The door for storing user data is kept open - but the question is where it will be stored 	
15	Create playlist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create: yes (series of videos, not of portions) • Share: difficult • Is on Europeana's User sets API roadmap • Edit / Montage (segmentation) 	Difficult to do Ash is checking what the timeline is <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pinterest • WITH
16	Adaptive Streaming?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • YT / Vimeo ToS don't allow it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TO-DO check which hosting platforms do allow re-skinning
17	Rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value? Rating needs critical mass 	
18	Stats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europeana has no statistics engine - only Elk stack • Allow open connections for what is being watched and why 	
19	Similar videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is done on Europeana (similar content) 	
20	Offline playback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No (only downloads) 	
21	Download segment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes (on condition of IPR) 	

Table 2: Functionalities as concluded at Kick Off Meeting

It was agreed that this long list would serve as the basis for the questions in the user consultation.

USER CONSULTATION: INTERVIEWS

A user questionnaire was drafted by ATIT and circulated to the partners on 9 October 2018. During the following week, the partners reviewed and refined the questionnaire, which resulted in the final

version that was used (see Annex 2: Interview and focus group questions) between 15 October and 9 November 2018.

ATiT, TIB and Europeana recruited users that represented their specific target group. Recommendations for the recruitment and carrying out of the interviews are given in Annex 2 on page 28.

General Public

The Europeana team recruited audience members via an online survey in which 28 users participated. The profile of these users reflects the typical profile of the online video consumer: 9 out of 10 users watch YouTube or other online video every day, 1 out of 10 at least once a week. The vast majority is a passive consumer: less than 1 out of 10 users upload their own videos for sharing on a regular basis (at least once per month), less than 3 out of 10 very rarely or occasionally upload their own video for sharing and more than 60% of video users never upload any video for sharing. More than 85% of video users never tag or bookmark a video or leave a note or comment. Only 1 out of 6 ever, rarely or occasionally make notes or bookmark videos. Not surprisingly, a similar pattern of use can be seen with the use of media metadata (75% of users never take note of the title or description of a video). Embedding and/or sharing the video on other platforms seems to be a feature that is more commonly used by the public at large: more than 6 out of 10 users more or less regularly embed or share a video that they find online with other users.

From these 28 participants, two participants were able to participate in the in-depth interviews. These interviews were carried out via Skype in the first week of November and were recorded for quantitative and qualitative analysis. The interviews lasted on average 63 minutes. The results are provided together with the results of the two other user groups in the comprehensive table on page 14.

Education Users

ATiT took care of the interviews of the education users. Recruitment of education users was aimed at professional educators (teachers) from compulsory education (primary and secondary levels) who are regular and proficient users of video in their teaching and learning materials in the classroom. For the recruitment we consulted the members of the Media and Learning Association via a limited survey in order to assess the interest and proficiency of possible interviewees. 26 People responded to this survey. On the basis of their representative profiles (interest, experience in the classroom, experience with the use of video), 9 users were invited to participate in the interview: 6 female and 3 male teachers. They teach different subjects from languages and art to maths and science, and come from Belgium, Ireland, France and Italy. The average age of the user group was 35. All 9 users declared themselves as making intensive use of video in their teaching practice. The interviews took place between 15 October and 15 November 2018 using Zoom and were recorded. Each interview lasted on average 71 minutes. The results are provided together with the results of the two other user groups in the comprehensive table on page 14.

Researchers

TIB looked after the researchers. A total of 6 interviews were conducted between 18 October 2018 and 7 November 2018. A pilot interview was conducted on 17 October 2018 prior to the actual interviews for the purpose of understanding how participants perceive the questions and how long an interview could take. The interviewees were researchers from Natural Sciences and Humanities. They all used AV media for their research activities both as producers of media and as researchers by means of media. The sample consisted of 4 female and 2 male respondents, with an average age of

43 from various domains of research (ethology, geography, history, pedagogy, film archives, languages) and nationalities (Hungarian, Germany, France). The interviews took place using Skype and lasted on average 67 minutes. The results are provided together with the results of the two other user groups in the comprehensive table that follows.

USER CONSULTATION RESULTS

Profile of the respondents

In this first part we provide an overview of the profile of the respondents.

The typical video platforms that were used by the respondents (in order of use, from more frequently to less frequently used):

- YouTube
- Vimeo
- VIAA
- TIB AV Portal
- archive.org
- Facebook
- Kahn Academy
- ksnapda
- moovly
- Netflix
- News sites
- SchoolTV
- Teleblik
- Visus
- VRTnws

Other resources that were mentioned only on one occasion: Agentur Karl Hoeffkes; BBC; Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung; Europeana; European Film Gateway; Film Treasure; iTunes; Liveleaks; Mubi; Radio; Steven Spielberg Jewish Film Archive; United States Holocaust Memorial Collection; Wochenschau Archiv.

Awareness of Europeana

It can be seen from the list of commonly used resources, the vast majority of respondents are neither aware and nor making any use of Europeana. When asked explicitly about their awareness of Europeana, the responses are largely negative.

Table 3: Europeana Awareness in Survey Sample

When novices are introduced to Europeana, all agree that it offers a great diversity of content which they need to explore it further and that "... there is a need to improve the image and visibility of Europeana." Respondents that are aware of Europeana comment that "... there is too much content and search options on Europeana are not ideal to find meaningful resources". They comment about the lack of user-friendliness, the information overload and the confusion caused by linguistic issues. The few regular users of Europeana visit the platform regularly for finding media contents for lessons, lectures, seminars, etc. One user commented on the peculiarity of the search functionality (search for colours...). The following suggestions were made:

- Improve Europeana's search performance: enable search for word similarity, typos, language versions of search term (Google Search like),
- Add metadata relevant to education or research domain (subject, description of content, age level, relation to curriculum...).

Results overview

In the table on the following page, we provide a comprehensive overview of all functionalities that were addressed in the interviews.

As mentioned before, these functionalities were extracted from the initial user stories that were drafted at the beginning of this project, then reviewed and refined during a face-to-face meeting with the Noterik and Europeana developers, where their feasibility and desirability were discussed. The purpose of the interviews was to ensure a better understanding of how and why users wanted these functionalities and to survey the degree of interest or need for each of these functionalities. Because users cannot be aware of the technical, managerial or legal issues that are related to the different functionalities, this list cannot be considered the ultimate wish list of functional specifications, but rather an indicator for the technical and managerial teams to understand how users work with video, what they would like to do with video resources and how important each functionality can be for them. This will help Activities 2 and 3 select and prioritise the most relevant design elements and functionalities of the EUPS that are accepted.

Results overview

#	Functionality	Education (n=9)	Research (n=6)	Total (n=E+R)	Public (n=2)
1	Add annotations (video)	8	6	14	
2	Add comments (video)	8	6	14	
3	Add annotations (segment)	9	5	14	
4	Add comments (segment)	9	5	14	
5	Add keywords (video)	6	4	10	
6	Store keywords (video)	4	5	9	
7	Edit keywords (video)	4	5	9	
8	Share keywords (video)	5	4	9	
9	Export bibliographic (meta)data (video)	6	5	11	
10	Export bibliographic (meta)data (segment)	n/a	5	5	
11	Display/view DOI/MFID	n/a	5	5	
12	Thumbnail images: snippet navigation	9	5	14	
13	Download still images	8	6	14	2
14	Download video	7	6	13	2
15	Download segments	3	6	9	
16	Embed video	7	6	13	2
17	Embed segment	5	6	11	
18	Display/view copyright information	6	6	12	
19	Display/view (existing) subtitling	8	5	13	2
20	Translate and generate subtitling	8	3	11	
21	In text search	9	6	15	
22	Enlarge view (zoom in on video)	3	6	9	
23	Increase/decrease speed	5	6	11	
24	Jump x seconds forward/backward	5	4	9	2
25	Store and recall personal information (search strings, results etc.)	7	4	11	
26	Create collection/playlist	8	5	13	
27	Display/view number of views	8	3	11	

Table 4: Survey results - overview

When arranged in order of consensus amongst all (education and research users), we see the following prioritisation by the users:

Table 5: Survey results – priorities according to survey sample

(*) The functionalities “Export bibliographic (meta)data (segment)” and “Display/view DOI/MFID” are only relevant to the research community.

None of the functionalities that were identified as potentially of interest to the users are completely irrelevant: none reaches a score of less than 60% when asked whether the user has experienced the need or interest in using one or the other functionality. In the summative table above, we do not make a distinction between education users and research users, as we don’t think it makes sense to build different players or interfaces for each user group. On the following pages, we will look at each of these functionalities in detail and add, where this is required, additional comments or requirements as expressed from the users.

Besides the functionalities that were presented to users, we also invited users to identify functionalities that did not appear in the long list of interview questions. We will comment further on these functionalities below.

FUNCTIONALITIES OVERVIEW

1. In-text search

Definition: using the search engine to find media that contain certain words or phrases. Ideally these words or phrases can be found inside any part of the media (text in image, text in metadata, text in speech, text in subtitles or transcript). Videos can be full-text searchable, with results highlighted in the navigable text and key marks on the timeline, synchronised with playback of the video.

User interest	Very high
Development	Not recommended (out of scope of EUPS)

This is a functionality that is regarded as highly desired by all education and research users. It should be noted however that this is not as such a functionality of the player but a functionality that needs to be supported on Europeana: it requires additional processing such as generating or retrieving transcripts from the content providers, uploading, indexing and interfacing, adapting the search engine. Alternatively, users can generate transcripts or enhance machine-generated speech to text results. This requires user management and quality control.

The users comment that they want to be able to search “in titles, key words, in descriptions, in subtitles, in transcripts, in text within images, in speech, in notes or comments”. It should be noted that this functionality is not uncommon to users that are working with educational video repositories such as MediaSite, Kaltura, Panopto etc. With Panopto, organisations can build their own private video repositories. Panopto furthermore includes SmartSearch, which is a video search engine that indexes the content within the library by using Automatic Speech Recognition, Optical Character Recognition, and content ingestion of slides or other documents.

-
- 2. [Add annotations \(video\)](#)
 - [Add comments \(video\)](#)
 - [Add annotations \(segment\)](#)
 - [Add comments \(segment\)](#)
-

Definition: annotation is a type of note or comment that a user can create and store for personal use based on time and spatial information within the media. Annotations provide a comment(ary) on the media or on a part of the media, acting as metadata (comments, edits, explanations) or as supportive text. An annotation differs from a tag which can be considered a label or keyword (see further below on the Keywords functionality).

User interest	Very high
Development	Recommended

Users comment that they would like to use annotations, notes and comments for personal use (not shared): they would like the functionality to add a comment or note to a media, inside or outside the media, which they can store for later reuse. If the annotation can be made shareable, it can become a low-level alternative for simple interactive video or it may allow commenting within a closed group. Public annotations or comments are not considered useful or desirable. As an alternative to commenting, some users suggested providing the option to link to social media to share media within a social media group (or even publicly) and provide comments in the social media space.

Annotation functionality is present in YouTube. Software annotation tools are also available as cloud services, as Open Source software (ANVIL or VATIC) or as part of video editing software such as Camtasia.

3. Thumbnail images: snippet navigation

Definition: thumbnail navigation or slider is an easy way to quickly navigate through a video by scrubbing the time slider (mostly found in the horizontal slider bar below the video) in order to visually search for certain images or sequences. Video thumbnails can also be useful in the catalogue view or the search outcome pages in order to give the user an immediate visual impression of the results of the search.

User interest	Very high
Development	Recommended

Users comment that they like fast visual identification by means of video thumbnails where possible: in the search results page, in the catalogue views, in the scrub bar or video timeline for individual videos. This supports fast searching and selecting between videos and inside videos. It helps with fast segmentation and can act as a surrogate for video summaries. Video thumbnails can also act as suggested videos (what to play next?) as in YouTube, but the function is controversial in education because it may be distracting.

4. Download still images

Definition: this is the option to download an image in jpg or another image format from an existing video. The image can be an image that is selected, prepared and provided by the owner or publisher of the video. It is also technically possible to create a still image by capturing the screen at the desired moment and export this capture as a still image. In both cases there may be copyright issues.

User interest	Very high
Development	Not recommended (legal issues)

Users, especially educational users, comment that they would like to use representative images for inclusion in their teaching and learning materials to refer to the media themselves, mainly to replace text links or URLs that are considered unappealing to the users. Users are unclear whether they are allowed to use the screen shots they make themselves of, for example, the opening play screen of a video or of any other print screen image they make from the video. They would like to see clearly if they are allowed to do so and if not, they would like to be offered an alternative image they can use as a placeholder or reference image, rather than being forced to create their own images. Almost all users declare that they are making screen shots now, even when they know it is illegal because of copyrights. For those video entries where there are no copyright issues, related to the download of a still image or the creation of a screen shot, the users would like to see a clear indication that such is allowed, for example by activation of the download button in the interface. The player should only provide this if rights allow it.

5. Download video

Download segments

Definition: this is the option to copy an entire video or a segment thereof, in order to store a local copy of the video for playback or further processing and/or editing at any other moment. In most cases there will be copyright issues: most providers do not allow downloading or any other use of their videos.

User interest	High
Development	Not recommended (legal issues)

Even though the users consulted all are based in institutions and organisations with what can be considered good or excellent access to the Internet, a great majority of them still declare that they would like the option to download a copy of the media on their own hardware. One of the reasons they give for this is the fact that, especially in schools, Internet access is often not stable enough. Another reason is that teachers want to be able to give the students access to the media after and outside the classroom and they cannot expect all students to have good enough access at their homes. Users also refer to the fact that e.g. in YouTube links may change over time, if they use learning materials from the year before, the link to the media may have changed and the lesson preparation or the lesson itself can be disrupted.

Some users want to be able to process the video for research or education purposes: they may for example want to download only the audio track for very detailed analysis and research, edit video to demonstrate certain educational topics (combine, compare, reflect, juxtapose...) or make mash ups as part of a creative and artistic learning path.

Downloading video segments or parts of a video selected by the user is considered useful or even required, mostly by researchers. This is not an essential functionality: in the rare cases where downloading is allowed, editing the segment out of the full-length video would also be possible.

Some users did mention the importance to be able to chapterise a video: to indicate one way or another (for example by means of markers in the timeline) the different parts of the video, if possible in combination with annotations or keyframes.

All users are aware of the copyright issues that can keep a video or segment from being downloadable. They are also aware of the technical solutions that may allow a work around, but are not keen on using these (horror stories exist in education communities and whether they are myths or truth, do seem to have an impact). All users request clear information with regard to the re-use that is allowed, for example by activation of the download button in the interface. The player should only provide this if rights allow it.

A solution that was suggested as an alternative to a simple download, was to create some kind of license like Netflix's, which allows playback of a local copy under certain conditions of use and the impossibility to copy, edit and/or distribute the media beyond the device(s) on which it was licensed.

6. Embed video

Embed segment

Definition: to embed video (or a part thereof) is the option is to add a video or other media together with the video player capabilities on a webpage using the playback resources of the video hosting service and without needing to add specific resources on the user side.

User interest	High
Development	Recommended

Users comment that they prefer this if downloading is impossible, but mainly for aesthetic reasons (instead of a text link), the users comment that this still requires good quality access at all times, which, despite progress in this area, is still considered an important issue. Segmentation of an embedded video (play from mm:ss xx:xx to yy:yy instead of playing the video at full length) is also considered highly desirable. The player should only provide this if rights allow it.

Embedding functionality is frequently used for sharing videos by means of social media (for example via closed Facebook groups). Some eLearning platforms or Learning Content Management systems that are in use in schools or school networks do not allow embedding of certain content (e.g. from YouTube). This can be a potential hindrance for use of embedding. Therefore, we undertook a small-scale survey to find out in how popular Electronic Learning Environments, or (Learning) Content Management Systems cope with the oEmbed standard. The table below provides an overview of the results of this sample survey (status on 28/01/2019). In this table it can be seen that in Primary and Secondary Education Learning Environments, oEmbedding is not widely accepted, while in Higher Education, it is the opposite result.

	oEmbed compliant	Coverage	Type	Target users
Google Class	Info requested	Global	free	All
WordPress	yes	Global	OpenSource	All
Scoodle	no	Belgium (Flanders)	Proprietary	Compulsory Education
SmartSchool	no	Belgium (Flanders)	Proprietary	Compulsory Education
EduMedia	yes	France, Switzerland		Compulsory Education
EduSharing	no	Germany	Proprietary	Compulsory Education
Edmodo	no	Global		Compulsory Education
Fidenia	no	Italy		Compulsory Education
WeSchool	no	Italy		Compulsory Education
Cumlaude	no	Netherlands		Compulsory Education
Magister	no	Netherlands		Compulsory Education
SOMToday	no	Netherlands	Proprietary	Compulsory Education
ZuluConnect	Info requested	Netherlands	Proprietary	Compulsory Education
ITS Learning (Fronter)	yes	UK, EU Countries	Proprietary	Compulsory Education
Moovly	no	Worldwide	free for education	Compulsory Education
Ilias	no	Germany (HE)	OpenSource	Higher Education
Stud.IP	no	Germany (HE)	Proprietary	Higher Education
Drupal	yes	Global	OpenSource	Higher Education
MediaWiki	yes	Global	free, open-sourced	Higher Education
Moodle	yes	Global	OpenSource	Higher Education
SlideWiki	no	Global	Free, open-sourced	Higher Education
BlackBoard Learn	yes	Global (HE)	Proprietary	Higher Education
Canvas	yes	Global (HE)	free, open source	Higher Education
Sakai	yes	Global (HE)	OpenSource	Higher Education
Dokeos	no	Global (corp)	Proprietary	Higher Education and Corporate
Easy LMS	no	Global (corp)		Higher Education and Corporate
Typo3	yes	Global (corp)	Proprietary/OS	Higher Education and Corporate

Table 6: Acceptance of oEmbed standard in educational platforms (sample survey)

7. Display/view (existing) subtitling

Translate and generate subtitling

Definition: subtitles are texts derived from the transcript of all spoken words in a video, sometimes complemented with descriptions of actions or situations within the images in order to support visually disabled users. Subtitles can be displayed at the bottom, the top or outside of the screen. Subtitles appear in sync with the video as it progresses.

User interest	High
Development	Recommended

Users from both education and research comment that they desire good subtitles as far as they are available, certainly for videos that are available in foreign languages that they themselves or their learners do not master. This is in order to access the content. Auto-generated subtitles do not have a good reputation. Educators see opportunities for learning and teaching activities in generating their own subtitles, editing and improving existing auto-generated subtitles, even in use of minimal subtitles (for example a keyword that appears in order to support apprehension).

8. Create collection/playlist

Share and/or copy collections/playlists

Definition: a playlist or collection is a list of videos that can be played back sequentially or in any other order. A playlist can also be a list of chapters or sequences as individual parts from other videos.

User interest	High
Development	Recommended

Users from both education and research consider it useful to be able to create playlists or collections of media. Preferably they would like to be able to add other media from outside the host repository to these (images, other media...) Playlists are considered useful for creating order in a string of media and for offering the string in the same or other order to other users (learners, colleagues). Playlists do not have to play automatically. If there is an auto-play function, it should be off by default. Collections are considered useful for building a private or shared mini repository within the larger repository (for example: one collection on the subject of Modern History and one collection on the subject of English Literature). Users would like to have the possibility to organise their collections as folders with subfolders (like in Windows Explorer). On the repository they want to be able to share the playlists and the collections, for example they share a collection with a colleague teacher of the same subject.

9. Display/view copyright information

Definition: copyright is the legal right that grants the creator or other rightsholder (publisher, editor...) of an original work the exclusive rights to grant other users permission to use the work in whatever mode of use: view, read, listen, edit, change, copy, make public etc. and all combinations thereof.

User interest	High
Development	Recommended

Users from both education and research do not look consistently for information about copyrights, but they would consider it essential to be able to easily find the information about possible and allowed use and reuse. During the interviews it became clear that users give a rather broad and flexible interpretation to the rights users have regarding the use and reuse of media from existing repositories. The terms “Fair use”, “Non-commercial” or “Use for education” were mentioned to describe a rather flexible or pragmatic way to use and reuse media, demonstrating the lack of knowledge about copyrights. Users prefer to receive clear messages regarding the use allowed by the copyright owner at the time when they inspect the media, and when they want to reuse the content (for example when they want to share or embed the media).

10. Export bibliographic (meta)data (video)

Export bibliographic (meta)data (segment) (*)

Display/view DOI/MFID (*)

Definition: bibliographic data are standardised references to a publication, originally mainly in print, but increasingly also in a digital format. They can appear as human-readable notations of data about the source such as author(s), title, year of publication, publisher, etc. They can also be expressed in alphanumeric strings or machine-readable codes. These bibliographic data make it easy to refer unambiguously to the source of a reference in another work.

User interest	High
Development	Recommended

Only a few users from education consider the use of bibliographic reference data important, because they use references to the sources they use or because they use them as examples for their students. They did not express any preference for a standardised format and only apply this to refer to the source in its entirety. In research, the large majority of respondents uses bibliographic references and/or metadata in standardised formats and identifiers such as DOI or MFID. They do not only want to refer to works in their entirety but also to specific segments. Some expressed the desire to work with a standardised and commonly accepted reference format in APA, MLA, Chicago or other referencing style in order to be able to cite immediately in a professionally accepted manner. In this context, it may be worthwhile to investigate the use of RIS as a standardized tagging format for compatibility with other digital artefacts.

11. Increase/decrease speed

Definition: Variable speed players can play back at a lower or at a higher speed.

User interest	High
Development	Recommended

Users comment that they would like this option for various reasons: faster to speed up searches or to compress viewing time (like in TED videos) or slower (if possible with pitch correction) to enable better comprehension (for example in explainer videos in physics education). Fast scrubbing through the progress bar is also a requirement. Play in reverse is not necessary.

12. Store and recall personal information (search strings, results etc.)

Definition: save individual settings and other data in a personal keep, for example a profile.

User interest	High
Development	Recommended

Most users would like to be able to keep personal data in a space that is accessible to themselves only, such as search strings, bookmarks, new search result alerts, collections, player settings (e.g. auto full screen).

13. Display/view number of views

Definition: indicate the number of times that a particular video has been played near the video (in the video display window) as well as in the search results or the catalogue views.

User interest	High
Development	(Not recommended – Europeana Policy)

This functionality is of more interest for the education users than for the researchers. Teachers argue that because they have little time, they use every possible indication that can help them to assess quicker whether a video is good. While they are aware that the number of views is not the most reliable indicator of quality, it gives them some indication of which videos have been used before, certainly within curated repositories (see also VIAA, KlasCement). Educators also like the possibility to like or rate a video, to share or recommend a video with colleagues, all in order to save time. Researchers are interested to see how many times their own videos are played by others.

14. Add keywords (video)

[Store keywords \(video\)](#)

[Edit keywords \(video\)](#)

[Share keywords \(video\)](#)

Definition: with keywords we mean the index term or descriptor that describes the topic of a media. Keywords in a repository form the controlled vocabulary that organise the media for search and retrieval by for example categories, catalogues or a search engine. Keywords and tags are used here interchangeably.

User interest	Moderate
Development	Recommended

This functionality is of more interest for the research community than for educators. While most teachers will use keywords for searching, they are not interested in adding or editing their own keywords or tags. The experience with user-generated tags (Teleblik) is not considered positive. The majority of researchers finds tagging important, few want to be able to create and edit personal tags and store them in their personal space. In general, the users consider tags to be more important in case they are publishers themselves. Only a small number of users want to be able to create, edit, store and share keywords.

15. Enlarge view (zoom in on video)

Definition: the possibility to magnify or enlarge the view of a selected detail of the video image beyond the maximum or full-size display of the video.

User interest	Moderate
Development	Not recommended

Users thought this functionality to be potentially interesting or useful. However, this functionality is of limited interest to the education community, except for some application in arts education. Researchers on the other hand all expressed their interest in the possibility to zoom in on parts of a video picture. If not possible to implement, all would be satisfied with full-screen view and videos of highest possible quality.

16. Jump x seconds forward/backward

Definition: by means of a single click instantly rewind or forward at once for a fixed duration of the video: most common time leaps are 15 seconds.

User interest	Moderate
Development	Recommended

Some education users thought this Netflix-like functionality to be useful for making transcripts or in language learning. A small majority thought the functionality would be desirable. If the scrub bar functions well, this time leap function would not be necessary, but it would still make a nice feature that has its uses.

17. Additional functionality suggestions from the users

Besides the functionalities that were presented to the users during the interview, we also invited the users to suggest functionalities that we had not presented in our questions. The following functionalities were suggested:

- "Suggest related media on the basis of similarity (Pinterest-like) and enable automatic sequencing (YouTube-like)"
- "Add interactivity (quiz, MCQ. linking) to video (Edpuzzle, Playposit, HiHaHo, Kaltura, MediaSite)"
- "If Europeana users need to login in order to retrieve media from Europeana, it is recommended to provide facilities for single sign on integration with the Virtual Learning Environment (e.g. with FB or Google account?)"
- "The interface or the player must provide a facility to allow users to send email feedback, for support questions."

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

The results of the user survey are in line with and largely confirm the initial functionalities list that was extracted from the first version of the user stories. This is to be expected: a common pattern of use of online media resources has evolved from the experience with the existing available media resources. Besides the standard functionalities that users like educators and researchers make use of in their daily practice (play, pause, scrub, full screen), they also want to use media in the same way as they use other content. With such content they are adopting web 2.0 functionalities, allowing for much greater interaction with the content, better usability, options for sharing and commenting, etc.

This has also become clear from the results of the user interviews. Functionalities such as adding, annotating and commenting, downloading or embedding, subtitling, creating and sharing playlists are important for users in education and research. These users are becoming aware of the technological feasibility of such functionalities not only from their day to day use of media platforms such as Netflix, Spotify, YouTube but also from their professional environments: media repositories such as VIAA, INA, TIB and virtual learning environments such as Moodle, SmartSchool, Ilias to name a few. The professional users in our target groups also express their interest in functionalities to manage citations (especially for researchers) and get clear information about the rights for use or re-use.

The comprehensive functionalities list gives an overview of the needs users have expressed during the round of interviews. These were presented by the Activity 1 team and discussed with the Activity 2 and Activity 3 team during the meeting in Hilversum on 21 and 22 November 2018.

As a next step, the functionalities are being reviewed in Activity 2 and Activity 3 to conclude which functionalities are feasible technically and acceptable for integration within Europeana. Some functionalities that are highly desired by certain users such as “Display number of views” for example may not comply with Europeana’s policy. The outcomes of this review process will be materialised in models or prototypes that can be evaluated in Activity 3, after which process they will be further developed in Activity 2.

ANNEX 1: USER STORIES (VERSION 1)

Education: Creating presentations with video in art education

During the first lesson period, Jonas a 29-year-old arts teacher who teaches 17-year-olds, introduces a learning activity. In two-weeks' time, the class will visit the Tate Modern Museum in London. The students have already learned about the history of modern art. Jonas prepares the students for the museum visit and asks them to individually create presentations about an artwork of their choice that is exhibited in the Tate Modern. Pupils can consult the website of the museum, or the catalogue of which four copies are available in the classroom. The pupils can also use for example Arttube videos they find on Europeana amongst all the other video's and media they can find there, they can also use any other additional sources (Vimeo, Wikipedia...) but with respect for the copyright situation at all times, to create a presentation no longer than 5 minutes in duration. The fact that the pupils and teacher access the videos on Europeana by means of the Enhanced Unified Playout Service has the advantage that they can easily cite from the videos and that they get instant and relevant copyright information. The students can use PowerPoint, they know how to integrate images, edit and embed videos, add an audio track, record a presentation, subtitle a video, publish and share the presentation. Each pupil works individually during the rest of the class period and at home to finalise their presentation before next lesson. The pupils share their presentations via the Learning Management System (LMS) SmartSchool within 5 days. The teacher reviews the presentations that were uploaded. He annotates the video and tags the video to facilitate feedback during playback. A few pupils are invited to present and comment on their work in front of the classroom. All pupils share their presentation with each other for review.

Education: Teaching and learning with video Karaoke style

In a class with 7 to 9-year-olds teacher Nele (45 years old) teaches about the museum. She starts class with a question round: "Who has ever visited a museum? What happens there? Who do you meet there? What do you see? Do you like to go there?" The teacher shows a video "Wie werken er in het museum?" ("Who works in a museum"? Arttube video on Europeana) and then the whole class discusses: "What do the director, the guide, the receptionist do each day?" The teacher refers to the parts in the video where these subjects are addressed. Next the teacher shows the video: "Kunstpraat met Paulo" followed by class discussion: "What is art? Who makes art? Can you make art?" Next each pupil creates an instant work of art. The teacher then plays the video "Het Boijmans Lied" ("the Boijmans Song", Arttube), first fully, then in Karaoke. The teacher has transcribed and subtitled the video in Dutch, all pupils sing along.

Education: Interacting with video in the arts class

Teacher Alia (36) introduces the subject of the lesson "Taking flight in art" with a class of 14-15-year-old pupils. This is a classroom experience and the teacher works with edited excerpts and/or a playlist. She shows a video montage she made herself of images, photographs, texts and parts of videos she has found amongst others on Europeana about art in exile, imprisonment or detention (for example "A fine line - Auschwitz in pieces of art" and "International museum for persecuted art"). During the class discussion, the pupils answer questions that are connected to tags within the video: the teacher has inserted multiple choice questions at certain points in the playlist or video, pushing specific multiple-choice question about the role that art can play for people in detention or

for refugees. While pupils are watching, they can tag the video in order to use parts in the class discussion.

Research: Scientific in-depth analysis of video sources

For her master thesis Melissa (24, Media Science, Film Studies) is analysing the phenomena of fake news in films from the First World War from an aesthetic perspective. Battle scenes from the First World War e.g. often do not show real battles. For the most part, they were shot away from the front during manoeuvres or performed specially for the camera. Such shots were usually edited together by producers with images of marching soldiers or destroyed buildings. These were then claimed to be news films that documented a military event of particular importance. Often the position of the camera indicates that a picture cannot have been taken during the actual fighting. Also the spoken text often doesn't match the action in the film. By using the new Enhanced Unified Playout Service that is provided on Europeana Melissa found a lot of relevant films, all assigned with a DOI/MFID so that she can cite them in a scientifically sound way in her thesis. Video segmentation and a scene overview based on pictures enable her to quickly scan through hundreds of videos. The subtitles help her create interrelations between spoken word and images and comprehend films not in her native language. Built-in zoom and slow-motion functions support her by helping analyse the position of the camera. She can also annotate areas in the video, which indicate a fake in the film and additionally extract and download those single frames to integrate them in her work.

Research: embedding of Europeana player to enhance publications and science blogs

Sam (47, Ethnologist, Researcher) is doing research in the field of ritual music and dance in New Guinea. Her research is presented through a variety of digital assets including text, videos and photos. She is publishing an article on her research in an open access online journal (e.g. viewjournal.eu), which allows for embedded media publication. On Europeana she found a variety of videos which demonstrate the use of drums and sticks for different religious occasions. Using the enhanced tools Europeana provides for AV like e.g. a scene overview based on pictures, she can quickly identify the relevant parts of the video. With the bibliographic metadata export she can export the video metadata into her reference management software Zotero including a Digital Object Identifier. With the enhanced unified playout service, she can embed the videos directly in the digital journal article. This is particularly simplified by the fact that license/copyright information about the video is displayed prominently. The reader can take advantage of the integrated Europeana player and doesn't have to move away from the text. Sam can also annotate and tag parts (both areas in a frame and time segments) in the videos in order to draw the attention of the reader to tiny details like different sizes and materials of the drum stick tips or the rhythm which is played.

Moreover, Sam is an active reader of various academic blogs at hypotheses.org. She is discussing with other scientists in the comments section and frequently points to additional sources that might help to improve the articles. She likes to use the tagging/annotation tool to add such remarks also to videos embedded in the blog articles.

Furthermore, Sam writes scientific and opinion articles on hypotheses.org blog regularly. She often embeds audio-visual material from Europeana as sources and illustrations of her articles. In order to contextualize the audio-visual sources, she uses the tagging/annotation tool that allows her to link related material to the whole video or single video segments as well as to annotate the video with her own interpretations. She also links to tags and annotations of audio-visual material that is

embedded in other blog articles. Both the provider of the original video source and Europeana receive usage statistics from the embed player regarding views and, if applicable, downloads of the respective videos.

European Citizens

Aubery is a marketing manager working for a film festival. He visits the Europeana Collections website after his friend posted a link on her Facebook wall about a new online exhibition on fashion, one of the themes of this year's film festival. He finds a video "Styl - Mladá móda" through the EUscreen collection. Aubery can play the video in Europeana, even though it is in fact hosted by the original provider, Czech Television. He can switch to the French subtitles provided through one of the subtitle-a-thons initiated by Europeana Media.

ANNEX 2: INTERVIEW AND FOCUS GROUP QUESTIONS

Activity 1 T1.1 Interview and focus group questions

During this task we intend to extract from the users (from the education domain, from research and from the public at large), their experiences with certain player functionalities as well as their expectations related to these.

From 15 October until 9 November 2018 ATiT, TIB and Europeana will each interview at least 6 respondents from their specific target user categories (ATiT: Education, TIB: Research, Europeana: Public at large) by way of interviews or focus groups. All partners will use largely the same protocol (questions and general approach).

Note 1: the questions are based on the conclusions of the functionalities discussion held during the Kick Off meeting. The list of functionalities herein is therefore limited to those that the technical partners considered to be potentially achievable, and/or for which user feedback would be useful. However, the list of questions is long (45 questions). This will require a high level of commitment from the respondent (and from the interviewer as well of course).

Note 2: this is an early user requirements survey, the outcomes of this survey will be fed back into the technical development team for review: therefore, the outcomes are to be considered provisional and open for discussion with the technical team.

You can choose to hold one on one interviews or focus groups, which can be considered in this case group interviews. Keep in mind that focus groups will require more time than individual interviews and they are best carried out by a team of interviewers.

Some recommendations:

Pay attention to the selection and recruitment of your respondents: the interviews will take an estimate between 90 and 180 minutes. We recommend dedicating a full morning or full afternoon to each interview.

This requires a serious commitment from your respondents. Please recruit respondents that are well informed about the effort that is required from them.

Make the interview as pleasant and comfortable as possible: choose a pleasant space where you conduct the interview, provide refreshments, foresee breaks, etc.

If the interviewer and the respondent decide beforehand that the effort required is too big or that doing the interview in one go is too difficult, you can decide to split up the interview in two or three parts and conduct them over more than one day.

Select respondents that have experience with the use of online video repositories (power users) and that are able to express what they do, how they do it and why in a comprehensible manner and in English. Acquaintance with Europeana is nice to have but not essential. Good expertise and acquaintance with use of online video is more important.

Make a PC with internet access available to your respondent, so that they, wherever this is relevant, can demonstrate what they are explaining. Make sure that you can make screenshots and/or screen cams from the user's demonstrations where you think this is relevant for your notes.

Make a recording (at least audio, if possible video) of the interview so that it is possible to go back and check certain parts.

Observe your respondent and take note where relevant of their attitude towards the functionalities and/or issues brought up.

We strongly recommend where possible to carry out the interviews face to face. If you decide to carry out your interviews remotely (via Skype or similar), it is strongly recommended to make a video recording of the call. Also enable screen sharing in that case so that you can follow and record also user demonstrations.

Be aware of the fact that remote interviews are much more tiring than face to face interviews, so you may have to decide upon a strategy to keep these to a level of effort that is manageable. Splitting the interview over two or more sessions is certainly a good idea in that case.

In order to keep the attention span more or less equal throughout the range of questions, you can decide to shuffle the questions from 15 to 45 so that every respondent receives the same questions but in a different order. This will compensate somewhat for decrease in attention span from both respondent and interviewer.

The interviewer can rephrase to some extent the questions to make them easier for themselves to ask, remember this is an oral interview and not a formal set of fixed questions in an online written questionnaire. Always keep in mind that what we want to achieve is a better understanding of what users expect from online video repositories, how they already use these now and what why and how they want to use them.

During the interview the interviewer can decide to skip questions that they feel are irrelevant for the respondent. It is recommended that in that case the interviewer takes note of what and why it was skipped.

Please ask the respondent whether he/she is available and willing to do a follow up interview if necessary at a later stage.

The interviews/focus groups can start from Monday 15 October onwards. Closing date for the interviews and delivery of notes from the interviews is Friday 9 November 2018.

Contact: mathy.vanbuel@atit.be

Questions Protocol

#	Question
1	Name and first name of the respondent
2	Profession/occupation
3	Organisation/institution
4	Country
5	Language
6	Age
7	Consent? (formally check, making clear how and where recordings will be used) (*) If needed use the consent form on the last page.

Where this is relevant, ask the respondent to show what they mean: have a PC at their disposal so that they can demonstrate with real examples of their practice. Make screenshots or screen movies for illustration.

#	Question
8	What does Europeana mean to you?
	Introduce Europeana briefly if the respondent does not know Europeana. If this is desirable, do a short demonstration of Europeana.
9	What experience do you have with use of online video and video repositories?
10	Which platforms do you use?

11	<p>Have you used audio and video on Europeana? (If the answer is no to this question, questions 12/13/14 can be skipped by the interviewer)</p>
12	<p>Why have you used Europeana video? Why not? For what did you use Europeana, and for what not?</p>
13	<p>How do you find the experience of using video on Europeana?</p>
14	<p>How does using video on Europeana compare with other online video and video repositories you use?</p>
15	<p>Do you want or need to add personal annotations or comments to (entire) videos (or other Europeana Media in general)?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used personal annotation already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
16	<p>Do you want to or need to add personal annotations or comments to video fragments or certain parts (hotspots? moving hotspots?) of the media?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used personal annotation or comments already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
17	<p>Do you want to or need to add personal tags to (entire) videos (or other Europeana Media in general)?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used personal tags already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>

18	<p>Do you want to or need to add personal tags to (entire) videos or to certain parts (hotspots? moving hotspots?) of the media?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used personal tags already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
19	<p>Do you want to or need to store and keep personal annotations, comments or tags for later?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
20	<p>Do you want to or need to share personal annotations, comments or tags with others?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
21	<p>Do you want to or need to export bibliographic metadata from (entire) videos (or other Europeana Media in general)?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
22	<p>Do you want to or need to export bibliographic metadata from video fragments or certain parts (hotspots? moving hotspots?) of the media?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>

23	<p>Do you want to or need to display and view DOI/MFID information from (entire) videos (or other Europeana Media in general)?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
24	<p>Do you want to or need to display and view DOI/MFID information from video fragments or certain parts (hotspots? moving hotspots?) of the media?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
25	<p>Do you want to or need to see thumbnail images from videos or media?</p> <p>How, where or when do you want to see these?</p>
26	<p>Do you want to or need to download thumbnail images from videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
27	<p>Do you want to or need to download stills from videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>

28	<p>Do you want to or need to download videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
29	<p>Do you want to or need to download excerpts from videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
30	<p>Which alternative scenarios would you apply if it is not possible to download a video or excerpts from videos?</p>
31	<p>For what reasons do you think it may not be possible to download video?</p>
32	<p>Do you want to or need to embed videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
33	<p>Do you want to or need to embed excerpts from videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
34	<p>Which alternative scenarios would you apply if it is not possible to embed a video or excerpts from videos?</p>

35	For what reasons do you think it may not be possible to embed video?
36	<p>Do you look for copyright information for videos or other media that you want to use?</p> <p>Do you know what the different copyright restrictions can be, for example as expressed in Creative Commons?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p> <p>How important is copyright information for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
37	<p>Do you want to or need to view subtitled videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
38	<p>Do you want to or need to create subtitles yourself for existing videos or parts of a video?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
39	<p>Do you want to or need to be able to search for specific words within videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>

40	<p>Do you want to or need to zoom in on videos or enlarge the view of parts of a video?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
41	<p>Do you want to or need to play videos at speeds other than normal? Faster? Slower? Reverse?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
42	<p>Do you want to or need to jump forward or backwards while playing a video? 10 seconds? 15 seconds? How long?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
43	<p>Do you expect to be able to store and recall certain personal actions, settings or other on the platform?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
44	<p>Do you want to or need to create playlists of videos?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>

45	<p>Would you like to know how many times a video has been accessed/played on the platform?</p> <p>Can you describe a case where and how you would do this? Tell us if and how you used this already. Why or why not? How often do you use this feature?</p> <p>How important is this for you?</p> <p>Essential – Useful and desirable – Unnecessary</p>
46	Open questions?

EuropeanaMedia Consent Form

You are invited to participate in an interview-based survey in the framework of the EuropeanaMedia project. The interview is being conducted by [name of interviewer], [organisation/institution of interviewer]. It should take approximately 135 minutes in total to complete. If it is agreed amongst interviewer and respondent, the interview can be split up in up to 3 sessions, taking place over different days. The interview may be carried out remotely via Skype or similar.

PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may refuse to take part in the interview or exit the interview at any time without penalty. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason.

BENEFITS

You will receive no direct benefits from participating in this interview. However, your responses may help us learn more about the use of media and video on Europeana.

RISKS

There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this interview.

CONFIDENTIALITY

This consent form, your interview answers and the recordings of your interview will be stored in a password protected electronic file store by the interviewer. The interviewer collects identifying information such as your name, email address, age, etc. These data are not transmitted further. For further processing the responses will be made anonymous. No one except the interviewer will be able to identify you or your answers, and no one will know whether or not you participated in the study. No names or identifying information will be included in any publications or presentations based on these data, and your responses to this interview will remain confidential.

At the end of the interview you will be asked if you are interested in participating in an additional interview at a later stage. There is no obligation to participate in any follow up activities.

CONTACT

If you have questions at any time about the interview or the procedures, you may contact [name] via phone at [number] or via email at [email address].

Your signature on this consent form indicates that

- You have read the above information
- You voluntarily agree to participate
- You are 18 years of age or older

Name, date, signature